

The role of authentic materials in teaching foreign languages (Chet tillarni o`qitishda autentik materiallardan foydalanishning roli)

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Abstract. According to the new objectives of teaching foreign languages , the task of a foreign language teachers is to provide conditions for familiarizing the learner`s personality with foreign language culture and preparing it for effective participation in the dialogue of cultures. The solution to these problems is to use authentic materials . Studies by a number of scientists show that working with variety types of authentic materials contributes to the increase in communicative motivation, has a positive effect on learner`s personal-emotional state.

Key words: authentic, motivation, creative, critical thinking

Abstrakt.Chet tillarni o`qitishga qo`yilgan yangi maqsadlarga ko`ra, chet tili o`qituvchisining vazifasi o`rganuvchilarni chet tili madaniyati bilan tanishishlari uchun sharoit yaratish, madaniyatlar muloqotida samarali ishtirok etishga tayyorlashdir. Bu muammolarning yechimi autentik materiallarni qo`llash hisoblanadi. Ko`p sonli o`rganishlar shuni ko`rsatyaptiki, turli xildagi autentik materiallar bilan ishlash kommunikativ motivatsiyaning rivojlanisiga hissa qo`shadi, o`rganuvchining shaxsiy- hiisy holatiga ijobiy ta`sir ko`rsatadi.

Kalit so`zlar: autentik, motivatsiya, ijodkor, tanqidiy fikrlash

Jadal qadamlar bilan kirib kelgan 21- asr hayotimizning barcha sohalarida, jumladan, ta`lim sohasida ham tub islohotlarni amalga oshirish zarurligini, ta`lim usullariga yangicha nigoh bilan qarash kerakligini taqozo qilmoqda. Bu o`qituvchilarga yanada mas`uliyatli, yanada tashabbuskor, yanada ijodkor bo`lish vazifasini qo`ymoqda. An`anaviy usullardan voz kechish payti allaqachon kelgani, “o`quvchilarni o`qitish emas, o`qishga o`rgatish” eng maqbul yo`l ekanini tajriba va natijalar isbotladi. O`quvchi darsda o`rganganlari real hayotda unga yordam berishiga ishonch hosil qilsa, ya`ni motivatsiya bo`lsa, darslarga qiziqishi ortadi. Chunki o`quvchi uchun sinf xonasidan tashqarida chet tili muhiti deyarli yo`q. Bizning vazifamiz har bir mavzuni o`quvchinig kundalik real hayotida har qadamda duch keladigan voqealarga bog`lab, ya`ni autentik materiallardan foydalanib tushuntirishdir. Buning uchun esa shunday kontekst yaratish kerakki, o`quvchi bu kontekst qaysi mavzuga oidligini bashorat qila olsun. Autentik materiallardan foydalanishning asl maqsadi ham shu hisoblanadi. Xo`sh, autentik material o`zi nima? “Autentik atamasi “tabiiy, original, hayotiy” ma`nolarini anglatadi. Autentik materialga matnlar, audio, videolar, gazetalar, qo`shiqlar, filmlar, reklamalar, teleko`rsatuvlar, xullas, real vaziyatda aniq maqsad uchun yaratilgan barcha narsalar misol bo`la oladi. Bildirilgan fikrlarni quyidagi misollar orqali tasdiqlamoqchimiz.

Aytaylik, “**Imperative mood**” mavzusini tushuntirish kerak. Buning uchun avvaldan tayyorlab qo`yilgan tarqatma materiallar- dori retseptlari, taom retseptlari, buyruq shaklidagi maqollar yozilgan varaqlarni, mahsulot yorliqlarini o`quvchilarga tarqatiladi. O`quvchilardan yozuvlarni o`qish va ular orasidagi umumiy jihatni topish so`raladi.

- Masalan:
- a) Take two pills a day
 - b) Don't iron!
 - c) When angry, count a hundred

Kutilgan javob: Barchasi buyruqni bildiradi

Bundan tashqari **turli situatsion** mashqlarni qo'llash yaxshi samara beradi. Bunda o'qituvchi o'quvchilarga quyidagi savollar bilan murojaat qilish mumkin:

What do I usually ask you to do?

Kutilgan javoblar: stand up, sit down, attention, go to the blackboard...

Undanda hayotiy misollar sifatida hayotimizda har kuni duch keladigan vaziyatlarga oid rasmlarni ko'rsatib, ularni qay holatlarda qo'llanilishini so'rash orqali o'tilayotgan mavzunung qanchalar hayotiy ekanini anglashlariga yordam beradi.

My favourite dish Pasta with bacon and tomato sauce

Ingredients

- 1 red onion
- 2 red peppers
- 120 g bacon
- 1 can (450 g) tomatoes
- 1 cup water
- olive oil
- garlic
- eggs
- 50 g pasta per person

Method

1. Cut the onion, red peppers and bacon into small pieces.
2. Heat some olive oil in a pan and fry the onion, red peppers and bacon.
3. Add **oregano, garlic, tomatoes and water** and cook for 20 minutes.
4. Cook the pasta in a big pot of boiling water.
5. Serve the pasta with the sauce, and enjoy!

Top Tips for writing

1. When writing a recipe or instructions, use numbers to indicate the stages and use the base form of the verb (imperative) to give instructions.
2. Use commas between things in a list. Use 'and' between the last two things.

Kutilgan javoblar:

- | | |
|--------------------------|------------------------|
| 1. during lessons | 5. giving instructions |
| 2. writing prescriptions | 6. warning |

3. giving directions

7. writing recipes

4. well-wishing

8. in proverbs

Turli o`yinlar ham grammatik mavzuni tushunishda yaxshigina vosita bo`la oladi.

GAME "DO AS I SAY" ("Aytganimni qil")

O`quvchilardan o`rinlaridan turadilar. O`qituvchi o`quvchilarga buyruq berish barobarida o`zi ham ma`lum bir harakatni bajaradi. O`yin qoidasiga ko`ra, o`quvchilar o`qituvchining bajargan harakatini emas, aytgan buyrug`ini bajarishlari kerak bo`ladi. Kimda-kim o`qituvchining harakatini takrorlasa, o`yindan chiqadi. Masalan, o`qituvchi "Touch your nose", ya`ni "Burningizni ushlang" deydi, lekin o`zi qulog`ini ushlashi mumkin. O`in bitta o`quvchi qolguncha davom etadi.

Berilishi mumkin bo`lgan buyruqlar:

Clap your hands!

Touch your ears!

Hands on waist!

Nod your head!

Buyruq gaplarning qay vaziyatlarda, qanday ma`nolarda ishlatilishi haqida ma`lumot berish orqali o`quvchilarni ushbu mavzuni o`rganishga bo`lgan qiziqishlarini oshirish mumkin. Xususan, buyruq gaplar quyidagi maqsadlarda qo`llaniladi:

-Giving commands

Speak only English!

-Granting or denying permission

Don` t take my book.

-Making requests

Pass me the salt, please

-Making offer or suggestions

Go to the theatre if you want

-Apologizing

Excuse me

- | | |
|----------------------|---|
| -Well-wishing | Have a nice day |
| -Inviting | Come to my house |
| -Giving directions | Take the right side |
| -Warning | Don`t touch the oven. It is hot. |
| -Giving instructions | Shake before drinking |

O`quvchilar bilimini mustahkamlash uchun turli mashqlar bajartirish mumkin.

ACTIVITY-1. Juftlikda ishlash. Har bir juftlikka buyruq gaplar yozilgan tarqatma materiallar beriladi. Ulardan berilgan buyruq gaplarni oqish va vazifasini aniqlash so`raladi.

- Handout 1.**
1. Have a cup of tea- offer
 2. Hurry - command
 - 3.Wait here for a moment - request or order
 - 4.Wash by hand - instruction

- Handout 2.**
- 1.Don`t turn the lights on! -command
 - 2.Post this letter, please - request
 - 3.Take the next turning– direction
 - 4.Boil at 120°C - instruction

- Handout 3.**
- 1.Look out! The bus is coming.- warning
 - 2.Enjoy yourself - offer
 3. Be a better cook- wish
 - 4 .Fall seven times, stand up eight! - proverb

- Handout 4.**
- 1.Go and buy yourself a book - suggestion
 2. Become the proud owner of a new sports car –well-wishing
 3. Stop whistling, will you?– request

4. Be my guest ! - inviting

Handout 5.

1. Help me with this letter –request
2. Don't walk on the grass –denying permission
3. Have another sandwich– offer
4. Lend your money and lose your friend - proverb

Handout 6.

1. Don't move - command
2. Make yourself at home - offer
3. Excuse me, it's my fault- apologizing
4. Press on this button - instruction

ACTIVITY –2. Guruh ishi. Sinfni kichik guruhlarga bo`linadi. Har bir guruhga berilgan vaziyatlarda buyruq gaplarning qo`llanilishiga doir poster tayyorlash vazifasi beriladi:

-imperatives used in public places (No smoking!, Value janitors` labour..)

-imperatives used in recipes(combine a cup of flour and the salt in a bowl...)

-imperatives used in proverbs (Live and learn, don't tell tales out of school...)

When students finish, they present their posters

ACTIVITY-3. Role - playing.

O`quvchilardan juft bo`lib, buyruq gaplarni qo`llagan holda qisqa dialog tuzish so`raladi.

Masalan, o`quvchilardan biri Londonga kelgan sayyoh va u Britaniya muzeyiga bormoqchi. Ikkinchi o`quvchi Londonlik rolini bajaradi. Sayyoh qanday qilib muzeyga boorish mumkinligi haqida so`raydi, mezbbon esa buyruq gaplardan foydalangan holda yo`l ko`rsatadi:

-Excuse me!

-Yes, Sir/Madam.

-I am a guest in your city and I don't know how to get to the British Museum. Will you show me the way, please?

-Of course. Go straight and turn the left. Take bus 16 and get off at the museum stop.

-Thank you

Har bir juftlik tayyorlagan dialogini taqdim qiladi. Qo`llanilgan buyruq gaplarni ko`rsatib o`tadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, o`quvchi o`rganayotganlari hayotida kerak ekanini anglab yetsa, o`rganishga rag`bati va darsga qiziqishi oshadi. Shuning uchun ham, darslarda, xususan, chet tili darslarida har bir mavzuni hayotiy misollar, vaziyatlar va vositalar orqali bayon etish maqsadga muvofiq bo`lardi.

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